

Research Article

Enhancing Biogas Production from Chicken Manure: The Role of Acid-Pretreatment and pH Optimization

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Abstract: Recent research has focused on anaerobic digestion (AD) for resource recovery from organic waste, producing biogas as a renewable energy source. The increase in chicken manure (CM) production, driven by rising global chicken consumption, raises significant environmental concerns if not managed properly. Anaerobic digestion (AD) technology offers a solution by breaking down CM to produce biogas, which contains methane (CH₄) that can be used as renewable energy. This study focuses on CM's physical characteristics and the effects of acid-pretreatment and pH on biogas production through the AD process. Standard methods were used to measure the physical characteristics of CM, including total solids (TS), volatile solids (VS), and pH. The biogas production experiments were conducted in Duran bottles at a mesophilic temperature range of 26°C–32°C. Biogas production was measured using the water displacement method, with daily records taken over 5 days. The results show CM's total solids (TS), and volatile solids (VS) values were 34.39% and 70.14%, respectively, indicating its suitability for biogas recovery. To enhance biogas production, acid pretreatment (1%, 3%, 5%) and pH optimization (6.5, 7.0, 7.5, 8.0) were studied, revealing that 5% acid concentration produced the highest biogas yield (23,133.0 mL on day 5), while pH 7.5 resulted in the highest recovery (83,650.0 mL on day 5). These findings demonstrate that optimizing acid pretreatment and pH conditions can significantly enhance biogas production from CM. The study highlights CM's potential in renewable energy production and its role in reducing greenhouse gas emissions while providing economic benefits to poultry farmers in Sabah, Malaysia.

Keywords: Anaerobic Digestion; Chicken Manure; Acid pre-treatment; pH; Renewable Energy

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1. INTRODUCTION

Renewable energy is crucial in our fight against climate change. It is derived from natural resources that replenish faster than we use them, making it a sustainable way forward. One promising source is biogas, which is produced through a process called anaerobic digestion (AD) (Ferreira et al., 2022). This method not only generates energy but also helps manage waste effectively. Rich in organic

matter, chicken manure (CM) is an excellent material for producing biogas. When microorganisms break down this manure, they create methane (CH₄) rich biogas, reducing harmful CH₄ emissions from manure storage (Firmo et al., 2022). The capture CH₄ can be utilized as a clean energy source for producing electricity, heat or fuel. Utilizing CM in this way not only offers a sustainable alternative to traditional energy sources but also mitigate greenhouse gases (GHGs) emission by preventing of CH₄ from untreated manure, contributing to more environmentally responsible waste management (Andrade et al., 2020).

To boost biogas production, several factors need to be considered for enhanced the biogas recovery. Acid pre-treatment involves breaking down tough materials in CM using sulfuric acid (H₂SO₄). Research by Mohammad et al. (2021) and Mrosso et al. (2023) shows that using high concentrations of acid and maintaining a specific pH level (between 6.8 and 7.2) can significantly increase biogas production. This process makes it easier for microorganisms to break down the material, leading to more efficient energy production. Besides that, optimizing pH level also plays a critical role in the efficiency of the AD Process. It is important as it can disrupt microbial activity, slowing down and even halting the digestion process in recovering the biogas (Wang et al., 2025).

Therefore, this study aims to systematically explore these variables of acid-pretreatment and pH to improve AD processes in recovering biogas from CM. By optimizing these factors, the study not only seeks to maximize biogas yield but also to improve the overall stability and reliability of the AD process. With also can be use in support renewable energy development, and address environmental issues related to CM disposal.

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

2.1 Sample Collection and Preparation

The main sample is raw chicken manure (CM). The raw CM was collected in Bukit as farm located at Putatan, Sabah. The sample was weighed and spread in thin layers for the physical characteristics determination.

2.2 Physical Characterisation of raw sample (TS, VS and pH)

CM was dried in the oven at 105°C for 24 hours. The purpose of this step is to determine the total solid (TS) content, which reflects the organic matter available for biogas production (Adjovu et al., 2023). The dried CM samples are then placed in a muffle furnace at 550°C for 4 hours to burn off the containing volatile solid (VS) in it. This additional step is for the determination of the percentage of the VS, which is the organic fraction that contributes to the biogas yield during AD (Wid et al., 2017; Abd Hammid et al., 2019). While, pH was determined by using a portable pH meter.

2.3 Determination of Biogas Production

In the acid pre-treatment optimization, CM was soaked in H₂SO₄ at concentrations of 1%, 3% and 5% (w/v). Each mixture was placed in Duran bottle and diluted water to final volume of 400 mL. The pH of each sample was adjusted to remain within 6.8 to 7.2 by using 1.0 M NaOH and monitored with a pH meter. The CM samples were incubated at ambient temperature (15 °C to 24 °C). Biogas was allowed vent through modified lids every 24 hours over a 5 days period. Biogas present was measured using a portable leak detector and total biogas production was calculated by using the water displacement technique (Selaman et al., 2024). The experiment was repeated for pH optimization (6.5, 7.0 and 7.5) for 5 days of AD.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Table 1 show the value of the TS obtained was 34.39%. This means that it is ideal to undergo AD as higher TS can lead to a higher organic loading rate (Marina et al., 2021). Biogas production can be increased potentially if managed correctly (Mohammad Kelif et al., 2022). However, it's not ideal to be dumb onto landfill because it is taking up space. On top of that, the value of the percentage volatile solid (VS) obtained was 70.14%, which indicates the suitability of CM for undergoing AD. Admittedly, the more organic nutrients for microbes, the more biogas can be produced. Besides that, study by Selaman et al. (2024) also had mentioned the methanogens work best in this range. The average pH value we obtained is to be 7.32. This pH value is not that far from the optimal Ph (6.8 to 7.2), so the use of chemical in controlled pH can be reduced.

Table 1. Physical properties data for current and previous study

References	Types of Waste	TS (%)	VS (%)	pH
Current Study	Chicken Manure	34.39±1.22	70.14±0.14	7.32±0.11
Selaman et.al (2024)	Protein-Rich Food Waste	34.16±0.08	88.5 6± 0.04	3.67±0.12
Mrosso et. Al (2023)	Kitchen Waste	36.20 ±2.34	96.36 ±1.73	4.00 ±0.00

Based on the Figure 1, acidic treatment of 5% concentration of H₂SO₄ produced the highest biogas (CH₄ gas and other gases) among the 1%, 3%, and 5% concentrations. This is showing 5% concentration of H₂SO₄ is optimum for digesting efficiently and breaking down more complex organic compounds in CM, making it easier for methanogenic bacteria to metabolize simpler nutrients and release more biomethane gas (He et al., 2021). Besides that, this finding shows that acidic pretreatment is crucial in biogas production for CM because it helps to break down complex organic compounds like lignocellulose, which are difficult for microorganisms to digest, and increases CH₄ production simultaneously (Xu et al., 2022). However, if the concentration of H₂SO₄ exceeds more than 5%, it might lower biogas yield due to overly acidic conditions that can inhibit microbial activity (Vidal-Antich et al., 2022). In addition, study by Selaman et al. (2024), also had mentioned 5% concentration of H₂SO₄ effectively breaks down complex organic compounds that can lead to facilitating microbial metabolism.

Figure 1. Effect of H₂SO₄ Concentration on biogas recovery in 5 days of AD

Figure 2 shows that a pH of 7.5 optimizes microbial activity for higher yield. In other words, a pH of 7.5 is the optimum pH for methanogenic bacteria to produce more biogas. In fact, during digestion with a pH of 7.5, the bacteria work more synergistically. According to other studies, it was stated that the pH for biogas production must be sustained within an ideal pH range for AD, which is pH 6.8 to 7.2 (Ali et al., 2021). The result we obtained is a pH of 7.5 that optimizes microbial activity for higher yield, which is closest to the ideal pH range for AD. Besides that, study by Selaman et al. (2024) also had stated that methanogenic bacteria are more active in a more neutral to slightly alkaline environment, such as in the range of 6.5-7.5. At this range activity is reduced because a more acidic environment can inhibit their metabolic processes. Therefore, biogas production will be low. On the other hand, at pH 7.5, biogas production becomes more because it is at the optimum pH.

Figure 2. Effect of pH on biogas recovery in 5 days of AD

4. CONCLUSION

The study found that treating CM with a 5% sulfuric acid solution significantly boosts biogas yields compared to lower acid concentrations. The CM samples showed total solids (TS%) ranging from 33.71% to 34.89%, with a notably high volatile solids (VS%) content between 60.29% and 69.14%. In addition, the average pH of the samples was found to be 7.5 indicating the optimal pH that supports microbial activity essential for recovering the highest value of biogas. Moreover, these findings indicate that the CM highly suitable for undergo AD leading to substantial biogas production. In addition, this research highlights the promising potential of CM as a renewable energy source, particularly through improved biogas production.

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